

RELIABILITY OF THERMOELASTIC STRESS MEASUREMENT.

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ABSTRACT

Since Spate became available, the thermoelastic effect has been exploited mainly to obtain the stress distribution in complex isotropic structures. On fibre reinforced composite systems the use of SPATE has so far been limited to simple comparative studies or to qualitative NDT-type applications. In this paper the significance of thermal conduction, surface coating, mean-stress, etc. on the spate data for both isotropic and anisotropic materials is investigated. A numerical model, based on the non-adiabatic theory, will be described and experimentally validated for different composite systems. Simulations show when valid stress data are obtained using SPATE on composite systems. Circumstances in which completely corrupted stress data are obtained are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The thermoelastic effect, as discussed here, describes the change in temperature experienced by a body as it adiabatically undergoes a change in stress. The theoretical treatment of this phenomena was first published by Lord Kelvin in 1853. He found a simple linear equation between the temperature change and the change of the sum of the principal stresses:

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T_0} = -\frac{\alpha}{\rho C_e} [\Delta\sigma_{11} + \Delta\sigma_{22}] \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the local cyclic temperature change, T_0 is the local absolute temperature, α is the coefficient of thermal expansion, ρ is the density, C_e is the specific heat at constant strain and $\Delta\sigma_{ii}$ is the sum of the cyclic principal stress amplitudes. The adiabatic working conditions require the loading frequency to be high enough in order to insure that the stress induced temperature change has insufficient time to diffuse within the material or to the environment. It is common to accept that loading frequencies of 2-8 Hz are adequate for most materials, e.g. [1] and that only for loading frequencies of less than 2 Hz corrections for thermal conduction effects are required, e.g. [2]. In this paper, an attempt is made to set the limits for the use of the Spate-technique for isotropic as well as for orthotropic materials.

ISOTROPIC MATERIALS.

A selected number of papers [3,4] confirmed the validity of the theoretical basis of the technique and demonstrated its scope and potential. In our case the reliability of Spate measurements on isotropic materials was checked using a SMC-bumper of a truck. The bumper was dynamically loaded in 3-point bending at 30% of the failure load and at a frequencies varying from 7 to 20 Hz. The Spate output was compared to rosette-type strain-gage measurements. The gage bonded in the middle of the bumper was used to calibrate the Spate-output. The variations of the sum of the

principal stresses calculated from the gage readings bonded on the left part of the bumper were compared to the calibrated Spate-output taken at the same distance but on the other side of the bumper. Figure 1 shows the test set-up of the bumper.

Figure 1. Test set-up of the SMC-bumper.

At all the frequencies the difference was within 5%. However we were particularly careful about the test set-up, indeed at 30% of the failure load no significant damage, causing local heating, is occurring and consequently thermal conduction is of no importance. Other important parameters are the surface coating and the mean stress-effect.

Surface coating.

The infra-red detector responds linearly to the changes in infra-red flux, $d\phi$. The Stefan-Boltzman law gives the relation between $d\phi$ and a small surface temperature change dT :

$$d\phi = 4eBT_0^3dT \quad (2)$$

in which 'e' is the surface emissivity and B the Stefan-Boltzman constant. For reliable measurements 'e' should be uniform and be as high as possible. This is achieved by painting the specimens with a high emissivity paint. Care must be taken in the application of the paint to ensure that just enough is applied to obtain a uniform emissivity, but not too much such that the paint is attenuating the infra-red signal. This issue was studied extensively by McKelvie [5] and Mackenzie [6]. It was found that the attenuation due to the coating increases with increasing frequency and increasing thickness of the coating and may become significant for loading frequencies > 30 Hz.

Mean stress dependence.

Results presented in Machin et al. [7] showed clearly that the thermoelastic parameters of the titanium and aluminium alloys tested specimens were mean stress dependent. Starting from the principles of basic mechanics and thermo-dynamics Wong et al. [8] treated the problem numerically and showed that the inclusion of the higher order terms could account for the observed effects. He showed that the thermoelastic temperature change under adiabatic conditions is given by the following relation:

$$C_{\sigma} \frac{\bar{T}}{T} = - \left\{ \alpha + \left(\frac{\nu}{E^2} \frac{\partial E}{\partial T} - \frac{1}{E} \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial T} \right) \sigma_{ss} \right\} \dot{\sigma}_{kk} + \left(\frac{(1 + \nu)}{E^2} \frac{\partial E}{\partial T} - \frac{1}{E} \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial T} \right) \sigma_{ij} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} \quad (3)$$

It may be seen from the above equation that by including the temperature dependence of the elastic properties, the statement of the thermoelastic effect becomes now a function of both stress and stress rate. Very good correlation was found between the non-linear effects predicted by the theory and those found by various experimental measurements. However, such non-linearities can make the determination of stresses by this technique much more difficult if the dynamic stresses are applied at a significant mean stress. It has been shown that the difference in the thermoelastic parameter from zero stress to yield stress is 40% for Ti-6Al-4V, 10% for AL-2024 and 14% for Steel.

Thermal conduction effects.

The effects of thermal conduction on the measured thermoelastic signal were first investigated by Belgen (1968). The experimental evidence of the influence of the lateral conduction is demonstrated by considering a thin plate connected to a much thicker plate simulating an infinite heat sink. In figure 2 the Spate output of a line-scan across the edge is shown for varying loading frequencies. These results clearly show a marked frequency dependence.

Figure 2. Spate line-scan for varying loading frequencies.

The effects of the substrate conduction, which depends on the through-thickness stress gradient of the component, was evaluated by considering an aluminium specimen with a blind hole. The specimen thickness was 10 mm and the hole depth was 8 mm. The results shown in figure 3 clearly indicated the presence of the hole.

Figure 3. Normalised Spate output for different frequencies.

COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Surface coating.

For carbon reinforced composite materials the emissivity enhancement is not required and consequently the specimens are not painted.

Mean stress dependence.

Similar results as for isotropic materials were reported by Dunn [9] on composite laminated specimens. However, for some of the laminates he investigated, he found that the results were biased by the effects of thermal conduction due to the different heats generated in the plies of the laminate.

Thermal conduction effects.

The adiabatic thermoelastic equation describing the temperature generated in a two-dimensional material due to the applied cyclic stresses in the elastic regime can be written as:

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T_0} = -\frac{1}{\rho C_\epsilon} [\alpha_{11} \Delta \sigma_{11} + \alpha_{22} \Delta \sigma_{22}] \quad (4)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 denote the longitudinal and transverse to the fibre directions respectively. However, it has been reported in [10] that the quantitative determined surface stresses, using eq. 4. compare very poor with the experimentally obtained thermoelastic data.

The classical lamination theory shows that depending on the fibre orientations, the ply-stresses and consequently the temperature generated in each ply may be very different. This results in high temperature gradients and significant thermal conduction in the through-thickness direction. So, for a more accurate representation of the problem we have to include the process of heat transfer between the different layers in the analysis. Since each ply can be treated as a homogeneous orthotropic plate, it may be shown from the principles of continuum mechanics and the thermo-elasticity of irreversible processes that, for quasi-static conditions and small temperature changes :

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} = -\rho C_\epsilon \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - T_0 (\alpha_{11} \dot{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \dot{\sigma}_{22}) \quad (5)$$

where q_i is the heat flux passing through the point under consideration, ρ is the density, C_ϵ is the specific heat under constant strain, T_0 is the absolute temperature, α_{11} , α_{22} are the coefficients of thermal expansion and σ_{11} , σ_{22} are the stress components in the respective inplane orthotropic directions.

If we assume the process of heat transfer to be dominated by diffusion in the through thickness direction, we may consider the development of a one-dimensional model.

Defining the non-dimensional temperature $q = \frac{T - T_0}{T_0}$ and taking the heat conduction equation of Fourier only in the through-thickness direction:

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} = -K_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \quad (6)$$

where z is the co-ordinate in the through-thickness direction and K_z is the corresponding heat conduction coefficient, we may modify equation (5) into the following form :

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} - \gamma \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial z^2} = S \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) is a classical one-dimensional diffusion equation where $\gamma = \frac{K_z}{\rho C_\epsilon}$ is the coefficient of thermal diffusivity and

$$S = -\frac{1}{\rho C_\epsilon} [\alpha_{11} \dot{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \dot{\sigma}_{22}] \quad (8)$$

represents the internal heat source.

The solution of this partial differential equation may be obtained by numerical methods. The

The solution of this partial differential equation may be obtained by numerical methods. The recommended method for this type of problem is a Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme. In contrast to the explicit difference scheme the implicit Crank-Nicolson scheme is unconditionally stable; the size of Δt is restricted only by the demands of accuracy, and not by stability. Convergence occurs always to the correct equilibrium solution.

The Crank-Nicolson finite difference representation of equation (7) may be written as :

$$\frac{q_i^t - q_i^{t-1}}{\Delta t} - \frac{g}{2} \left\{ \frac{(q_{i+1}^t - 2q_i^t + q_{i-1}^t) + (q_{i+1}^{t-1} - 2q_i^{t-1} + q_{i-1}^{t-1})}{(\Delta z)^2} \right\} = S_i \quad (9)$$

in which the subscript i indicates the position on z -axis and the superscript t the position in time, Δz and Δt are corresponding spatial and time increments.

Grouping the corresponding terms yields :

$$q_{i-1}^t + Aq_i^t + q_{i+1}^t = B_i$$

where,

$$A = -2 \left(1 + \frac{(\Delta z)^2}{g \Delta t} \right)$$

$$B_i = \frac{-2(\Delta z)^2}{g} S_i - q_{i-1}^{t-1} + 2 \left(1 + \frac{(\Delta z)^2}{g \Delta t} \right) q_i^{t-1} - q_{i+1}^{t-1} \quad (10)$$

To obtain a solution, initial and boundary conditions are required. At $t = 0$, we assume the body to be in thermal equilibrium with the surrounding, so that $q(x=x_i, t=0) = 0$.

As we only studied laminates which have symmetry about their mid planes, we assume adiabatic boundary conditions on the mid plane. On the free surface, we assume convective boundary conditions.

The obtained tridiagonal set of 'n' equations in q_i , may be solved efficiently by well known algorithms.

In order to solve the non-adiabatic thermoelastic problem the source-term S (cfr. eq. 8) has to be determined for every layer. Assuming on the specimen an applied uniaxial sinusoidal load of the form $F = F_0 + \Delta F \sin \omega t$, where ΔF is the load amplitude, the derivative of the stress with respect to time may be written as :

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ii} = \Delta \sigma_{ii} \omega \cos \omega t \quad (11)$$

where, the stress amplitude in the fibre direction ($\Delta \sigma_{11}$) and perpendicular to the fibre direction ($\Delta \sigma_{22}$) may be calculated from the classical lamination theory.

Substitution of equation (11) into equation (8) gives :

$$S = \frac{-1}{\rho c_E} \omega \cos \omega t [\alpha_{11} \Delta \sigma_{11} + \alpha_{22} \Delta \sigma_{22}] \quad (12)$$

From equation (10) and (12) we can proceed to solve the thermoelastic problem. The code, developed to run on a PC, discretises each ply by 20 nodes and uses a time-step of $0.01 \pi/\omega.s$ (period / 200) for all frequencies studied. At every time step the complete temperature field was solved.

Figure 3 shows the temperature profile across the thickness of the specimen of a $[0^\circ, 90^\circ, 2, 0^\circ]_S$ CFRP-laminate. The temperature plotted in ordinate represents the temperature across the thickness at the moment of maximum surface temperature within the last period calculated and for an arbitrary cyclic stress-amplitude of 1N/mm^2 .

Figure 3. The temperature profile across the thickness of a $[0^\circ, 90^\circ, 2, 0^\circ]_S$ CFRP-laminate.

In abscissa scale $z=0$ represents the free surface, while $z=1$ corresponds to the plane of symmetry. It is easily seen, that even though the source term is, for layers with different fibre orientation, a discontinuous function, the temperature profiles across the thickness are smoothly continuous as a result of diffusion. At low frequencies, for instance 1 Hz, significant conduction can take place and the temperature is nearly equally distributed over all the points in the through-thickness direction. When the frequency is increased, the time scale becomes more contracted and consequently less conduction is allowed, resulting in higher temperature gradients. The higher temperature in the 90° -plies (second and third ply) has not enough time to conduct to the surface, resulting in a lower surface temperature. It is also seen from figure 3 that even at 20 Hz which is the maximum loading frequency of the used MTS-machine, the temperature profile is still very different from the step function representing the adiabatic process (cfr. frequency of 100 Hz.). To illustrate how dramatic through-thickness conduction can influence the recorded surface temperature a quasi-isotropic specimen with different stacking sequences was considered. Figure 4 shows both the experimental (filled symbols) and the numerical Spate output for the different stackings. All the amplitude data are normalised by the Spate data at 20 Hz.

Figure 4. Normalised amplitude for different quasi-isotropic laminates.

Motion effect

Van Hemelrijck *et al.* [11] studied the effects of motion coupled with a mean temperature change due to damage and showed that even small local oscillations, coupled with the presence of just moderate temperature gradients (as a result of irreversible internal heat generation), can produce a significant component which can totally corrupt the stress induced signal.

CONCLUSIONS

Although the great potentials of SPATE for experimental stress analysis are commonly accepted, in this paper it is shown that certainly thermal conduction effects may not be neglected when performing stress analysis by thermoelastic techniques. Typically in regions where the stress gradients are high, thermal conduction will bias an accurate stress measurement. Due to high through-thickness stress gradients in many composite laminates such thermal conduction effects cannot be considered as 'second-order' effects. They are very significant.

The mathematical model developed for composite laminates showed how thermal conduction affects the surface temperature and demonstrated very good agreement with the experimental results.

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CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES
